

From Advisory Silence to Judicial Finality : Comparing the 1993 Presidential Reference and the 2019 Ayodhya Judgment

Paper Id : 19838 Submission Date : 2025-06-07 Acceptance Date : 2025-06-21 Publication Date : 2025-06-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17052918

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Sarita Paul

Assistant Professor
Department Of Law
PURC
Ludhiana, Punjab, India

Abstract

The Babri Masjid–Ram Janmabhoomi dispute in Ayodhya stands as one of the most complex and sensitive constitutional controversies in India, testing the boundaries of judicial function, secular governance, and faith-based claims. The present study undertakes a comparative analysis of two critical judicial moments. The first is the 1993 Presidential Reference under Article 143, where the Supreme Court declined to answer the question of whether a Hindu temple existed prior to the Babri Masjid, citing the impropriety of intervening in matters sub judice and the dangers of fact-finding through advisory jurisdiction. The second is the 2019 Supreme Court judgment, which delivered a final, unanimous verdict on the title dispute by awarding the disputed land to Ram Lalla Virajman while directing the allocation of alternate land to the Sunni Waqf Board. By contrasting the Court's self-imposed restraint in 1993 with its decisive adjudication in 2019, the study highlights the evolution of judicial strategy from non-intervention to conclusive settlement.

Keywords

Advisory Opinion, Communal, Constitution, Faith, Secularism.

Introduction

Historical Background of the Dispute

In the year 1528, during the early years of the Mughal Empire in India, a mosque known as the Babri Masjid was constructed in the town of Ayodhya, in present-day Uttar Pradesh. It was built by Mir Baqi, a commander in the army of the first Mughal Emperor Babur. The mosque was named Babri Masjid after Babur himself. According to some historical accounts and inscriptions (which are debated), Mir Baqi built the mosque on the orders of Babur. Hindu groups have long claimed that the mosque was built after demolishing a pre-existing Hindu temple at the site, which they believe marked the birthplace of Lord Ram (Ram Janmasthan).[1] However, Muslim groups denied this claim, stating that the mosque was constructed on vacant land and had stood as a place of worship for centuries. The claim that a temple was demolished to build the mosque is not unanimously accepted among historians. During the litigation, the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) conducted an excavation (2003) and reported the presence of a non-Islamic structure beneath the mosque, which became crucial in the legal battle. By the 1850s, the site of the Babri Masjid in Ayodhya had become a source of religious tension between Hindus and Muslims. Hindus had begun to claim that the mosque stood on the exact birthplace of Lord Ram, and some had started worshipping outside the mosque premises, at a platform known as "Ram Chabutra". Muslims, on the other hand, continued offering namaz inside the mosque, which they had done for centuries.[2] In 1855 communal violence was recorded between Hindus and Muslims in Ayodhya over access to the site. The British colonial administration, which governed India at that time, attempted to maintain order by placing a physical railing or fence to separate the inner courtyard (used by Muslims) and the outer courtyard (where Hindus were allowed to worship). This was the first documented evidence of religious conflict over the Babri Masjid–Ram Janmabhoomi site. The British strategy of allowing parallel worship laid the groundwork for later legal claims by both communities, and the site became officially "disputed." It was also the beginning of a long history of communal tension centred on the religious and historical significance of the site.

Objective of study

The Babri Masjid–Ram Janmabhoomi dispute in Ayodhya stands as one of the most complex and sensitive constitutional controversies in India, testing the boundaries of judicial function, secular governance, and faith-based claims. The present study undertakes a comparative analysis of two critical judicial moments. The first is the 1993 Presidential Reference under Article 143, where the Supreme Court declined to answer the question of whether a Hindu temple existed prior to the Babri Masjid, citing the impropriety of intervening in matters sub judice and the dangers of fact-finding through advisory jurisdiction. The second is the 2019 Supreme Court judgment, which delivered a final, unanimous verdict on the title dispute by awarding the disputed land to Ram Lalla Virajman while directing the allocation of alternate land to the Sunni Waqf Board. By contrasting the Court's self-imposed restraint in 1993 with its decisive adjudication in 2019, the study highlights the evolution of judicial strategy from non-intervention to conclusive settlement.

Review of Literature

New Legal battles and Communal Clashes over Ram Janmabhoomi-Babri Masjid after Independence of India

Night of 22–23 December 1949 the Idols of Lord Ram and Sita were surreptitiously placed inside the central dome of the Babri Masjid, reportedly under the main dome,

which was later claimed to be the Ram Janmasthan (birthplace of Lord Ram).[3] The incident took place at night, allegedly by Hindu activists, without any legal authority. The next morning, Hindu devotees began gathering, claiming that Lord Ram had “miraculously appeared” inside the mosque. This led to an outburst of religious excitement among Hindus and strong objections from the Muslim community. The then District Magistrate of Faizabad, K.K. Nayar, refused to remove the idols, citing law and order concerns. The Government of Uttar Pradesh declared the site “disputed” and invoked Section 145 of the Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) to prevent further conflict. The Babri Masjid was locked down, and both communities were prohibited from entering. However, Hindu priests were allowed to perform worship of the idols from outside the locked premises. In 1950, the first of several civil suits was filed by a Hindu devotee, Gopal Singh Visharad,[4] seeking the right to worship the idols inside the structure. Over the following decades, multiple title suits were filed by Hindu and Muslim parties claiming ownership of the land. This incident transformed the mosque into a contested religious site. The event froze the status quo and set the stage for the dispute to escalate politically, legally, and communally in the years to come.

Unlocking of the Site for Hindu Worship

1 February 1986; A district judge in Faizabad, K.M. Pandey, passed an order directing that the locks on the Babri Masjid premises be removed. This allowed Hindu devotees to have unrestricted access to worship the idols of Ram Lalla that had been placed inside the structure in 1949. Since the 1949 idol placement, the inner courtyard of the Babri Masjid had been locked to prevent clashes between Hindus and Muslims. Hindu devotees could only worship from a distance outside the locked gates. In 1986, lawyer Umesh Chandra Pandey filed a petition before the Faizabad district court seeking the right for Hindus to worship inside. District Judge Pandey stated that since the idols had been in the disputed structure for decades, “keeping the premises locked was an unnecessary restriction”. He ordered the locks to be removed immediately, enabling direct worship inside the structure.[5] Within hours, television cameras broadcast the unlocking live, a first in Indian media, leading to celebrations among Hindu groups. Muslim organizations protested strongly, arguing that this was a violation of their rights and the status quo. The Babri Masjid Action Committee was formed to advocate for the Muslim claim. It marked the beginning of the mass mobilization for the Ram Janmabhoomi movement, spearheaded by Hindu nationalist organizations. This also set the stage for the large-scale political and communal mobilization that culminated in the events of 1990 and 1992.

Demolition of the Babri Masjid 6 December 1992

On this day, the Babri Masjid in Ayodhya was demolished by a large crowd of Kar Sevaks (Hindu volunteers) who had gathered for the Ram Janmabhoomi movement. The demolition took place during a political rally organized by the Vishwa Hindu Parishad (VHP) and supported by the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) and other Hindu nationalist groups. Top political leaders like L.K. Advani, Murli Manohar Joshi, and Uma Bharti were present at the site, addressing the assembled crowd. Despite assurances to the Supreme Court and the Government of India that the mosque would not be harmed, the atmosphere was charged. Thousands of Kar Sevaks broke through security barriers and began attacking the Babri Masjid with hammers, rods, and other tools. Within a few hours, the 500-year-old structure was reduced to rubble. An idol of Ram Lalla was placed at the spot where the mosque once stood, and continuous worship began. The demolition triggered widespread communal riots across India.[6] Major cities like Mumbai, Delhi, Bhopal, Surat, and Kanpur witnessed severe violence. According to official estimates, over 2,000 people died in the aftermath, most of them in Mumbai and other urban areas. The demolition was condemned nationally and internationally. Cases against thousands of unnamed Kar Sevaks for destruction of property and promoting enmity between communities was registered.[7] The Liberhan Commission was set up in 1992 to investigate the events, it submitted its report in 2009, holding several political and religious leaders responsible. The title suit over the land was unaffected in its legal course and continued in the Allahabad High Court. The demolition marked the most explosive escalation of the Ram Janmabhoomi–Babri Masjid dispute. It permanently altered Hindu-Muslim relations in India. It shifted the Ayodhya dispute from a localized religious-legal issue into a national political and communal flashpoint.

Title Suits and Criminal Cases were Filed after December 6, 1992

Hindu parties (like Ram Lalla Virajman, Nirmohi Akhara, and individual devotees) claimed the site as Ram Janmabhoomi and sought control to build a temple. Muslim parties (mainly the Sunni Central Waqf Board) claimed the land as waqf property for a mosque. After the demolition, these pending suits were consolidated and heard together by the Lucknow Bench of the Allahabad High Court. Case on the demolition incident, against unnamed Kar Sevaks, for the physical destruction of the mosque and case against political and religious leaders, for alleged criminal conspiracy, incitement to violence, and communal provocation were filed. Key accused included L.K. Advani, Murli Manohar Joshi, Uma Bharti, and leaders of the VHP. In 2020, a special CBI court acquitted all accused leaders, citing lack of conclusive evidence of a planned conspiracy.

Liberhan Commission of Inquiry 1992–2009

The Government of India set up the Liberhan Commission[8] within 10 days of the demolition. Justice M.S. Liberhan submitted the report in 2009 (after 17 years of inquiry). Held that the demolition was "neither spontaneous nor unplanned", but the result of a meticulously planned campaign. Named 68 individuals, including BJP and VHP leaders, as responsible. While the criminal cases addressed accountability for the demolition, the title suits focused on ownership of the land. This dual legal track continued until the 2010 Allahabad High Court judgment, which partially resolved the title dispute but was appealed to the Supreme Court.[9]

1993 Presidential Reference on the Ayodhya Dispute

The Babri Masjid was demolished, triggering nationwide communal riots. The Government of India sought to address one core controversy i.e. did a Hindu temple or religious structure exist at the site before the Babri Masjid was built? President Dr. Shankar Dayal Sharma used Article 143(1)[10] of the Constitution to seek the Supreme Court's advisory opinion. The Question Referred "Whether a Hindu temple or any Hindu religious structure existed prior to the construction of the Ram Janmabhoomi-Babri Masjid (including the mosque known as Babri Masjid) at the disputed site in Ayodhya?"[11] At the hearing, it was strenuously urged that the question of fact referred under Article 143(1) of the Constitution is vague; the answer to it is by itself not decisive of the real controversy since the core question has not been referred; and it also gives no definite indication of the manner in which the Central Government intends to act after the Special Reference is answered, to settle the dispute. It was urged that the question referred is, therefore, academic, apart from being vague, and it does not serve any constitutional purpose to subserve which the advisory jurisdiction of this Court could be invoked; that the real object and purpose of reference is to take away a place of worship of the Muslims and give it away to the Hindus offending the basic feature of secularism; and that, therefore, we should decline to answer the Special Reference.[12] During Ismail Faruqi Case[13], the learned Solicitor General who appeared for the Union of India was asked to clarify the stand of the Central Government on this point. Initially, it was stated by the learned Solicitor General that the answer to the question would provide the basis for further negotiations between the different groups to settle the controversy and the Central Government would then be able to decide the effective course available to it for resolving the controversy. On being asked to further clarify the stand of the Central Government about the purpose of the Special Reference, the learned Solicitor General made a statement in writing on behalf of the Union of India on 14th September, 1994 as under: Government stands by the policy of secularism and of even-handed treatment of all religious communities. The Acquisition of Certain Area at Ayodhya Act, 1993, as well as the Presidential Reference, have the objective of maintaining public order and promoting communal harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst the people of India. [14] Government is committed to the construction of a Ram temple and a mosque, but their actual location will be determined only after the Supreme Court renders its opinion in the Presidential Reference. Government will treat the finding of the Supreme Court on the question of fact referred under Article 143 of the Constitution as a verdict which is final and binding.

In the light of the Supreme Court's opinion and consistent with it, Government will make efforts to resolve the controversy by a process of negotiations. Government is confident that the opinion of the Supreme Court will have a salutary effect on the attitude of the communities and they will no longer take conflicting positions on the factual issue settled by the Supreme Court. If efforts at, a negotiated settlement as aforesaid do not succeed, Government is committed to enforce a solution in the light of the Supreme Court's opinion and consistent with it. Government's action in this regard will be even-handed in respect of both the communities. If the question referred is answered in the affirmative, namely, that a Hindu temple/structure did exist prior to the construction of the demolished structure, Government action will be in support of the wishes of the Hindu community. If, on the other hand, the question is answered in the negative, namely, that no such Hindu temple/ structure existed at the relevant time, then Government action will be in support of the wishes of the Muslim community.[15] This statement in writing made by the learned Solicitor General on behalf of the Union of India forms a part of the record and has to be taken into account to indicate the purpose for which the Special Reference under Article 143(1) has been made to this Court.

In the second point they discussed that the matter regarding reference to be decided after hearing the parties and the response of the referred question will be filed in the Court with the Affidavit. The reference holds no ground today as the matter stands decided by the Supreme Court, on the factual issue of whether there existed a Hindu temple or Babri Masjid on the disputed land. This is the only reference till date which was returned unanswered by the Supreme Court.[16] The court rejected the reference firstly the matter was already under litigation and the court is not empowered to any such question under article 143, secondly the court could foresee the reference opinion being misused by the government in the ongoing negotiation between the parties, thirdly the reference was framed in a way that favoured one of the parties to the dispute. Therefore, the court found it apt to not answer the reference. This reference was returned back for the directions March 16, 1993. Established that the Court will avoid fact-specific or evidence-heavy historical questions when regular judicial proceedings are already in motion. The main Ayodhya dispute continued in the Allahabad High Court without this advisory input.

M. Siddiq (D) Thr Lrs v. Mahant Suresh Das & Ors[17]

The case concerned the 2.77 acres disputed land in Ayodhya, claimed by both Hindus (as the birthplace of Lord Ram, Ram Janmabhoomi) and Muslims (as the site of Babri Masjid built in 1528). Multiple title suits were filed, consolidated, and decided by the Allahabad High Court in 2010, which ordered a three-way division of land. Appeals against this verdict reached the Supreme Court, which delivered its final judgment in 2019. First issues before the Court was that who holds the title/ownership of the disputed land? Secondly whether the 1949 idol placement and the 1992 demolition affected the legal rights of parties? Thirdly how should the Court balance faith-based claims with constitutional principles?

Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) Report considered as evidence of a non-Islamic structure beneath the mosque. This report not conclusive that it was a Ram temple, but sufficient to suggest pre-existing religious activity. However, placing idols in 1949 and demolition in 1992 were declared illegal acts. But these did not extinguish Hindu parties' claims of possession and worship rights. Court held that while faith cannot determine title, the long, continuous Hindu belief and worship at the site carried evidentiary value. Judgment (Unanimous) Disputed land (2.77 acres) was handed over to Ram Lalla Virajman (deity, represented by a trust to be formed by Government of India). Recognized deity as a juristic person with legal rights. Sunni Waqf Board to be allotted 5 acres of land in Ayodhya at a prominent site for construction of a mosque. Directed the Union Government to create a trust within 3 months to manage and oversee construction of a Ram temple at the disputed site. Two clear views emerged, first is the Supreme Court resolved a highly complex conflict concerning the title of a disputed property, balancing historical claims, religious sentiments, and legal principles. Secondly the Supreme Court's judgment in the Ayodhya title dispute has been criticized for being majoritarian in character, representing what some have described as "the victory of faith over facts." Critics argue that the verdict unduly favored the Hindu community over the Muslim community, notwithstanding the secular credentials of the Indian State, and in effect rewarded parties that had engaged in the demolition of the Babri Masjid, a blatant violation of the rule of law. Such an outcome raises fundamental questions about the Court's ability to act as a counter-majoritarian institution and safeguard constitutional morality against majoritarian tyranny. Justice, in its truest sense, cannot overlook issues of law and order, constitutional fidelity, or the legacy of violence that marked the dispute. Yet, the judgment appeared to hasten towards a resolution that aligned with majoritarian sentiments, sentiments cultivated and sustained by the political project of Hindutva.

Advisory Silence to Judicial Finality

Comparison between the Judgements of Supreme Court in 1993 Presidential Reference on the Ayodhya Dispute and M. Siddiq (D) Thr. Lrs. v. Mahant Suresh Das & Ors cases highlight how the Court treated the same dispute differently in its advisory and adjudicatory roles. Firstly, the Presidential Reference was invoked under Article 143 of the Constitution, which confers advisory jurisdiction on the Supreme Court. The question posed was: "Whether a Hindu temple or any Hindu religious structure existed prior to the construction of the Ram Janmabhoomi–Babri Masjid (1528) in Ayodhya?" The Court declined to answer, holding that giving an opinion would not serve any constitutional purpose and could prejudice pending suits. In contrast, the M. Siddiq case was a regular civil appeal arising from suits filed in the Allahabad High Court. Here, the Supreme Court exercised its adjudicatory jurisdiction under Articles 131 and 136, and had to finally decide the title dispute over the 2.77 acres of disputed land. Secondly, in the Presidential Reference the Court stressed judicial restraint and refused to act as a fact-finding body for historical or religious disputes. It emphasized that its role was not to resolve political or religious controversies through advisory opinions. In the M. Siddiq case, however, the Court adopted an adjudicatory approach, analysing archaeological reports (ASI), historical records, revenue documents, and witness testimony. The Court sought to balance faith and law, acknowledging Hindu belief in Ram Janmabhoomi while also addressing Muslim claims to possession. Thirdly, in the advisory opinion, the Court underscored the secular character of the Indian State and avoided legitimizing religious majoritarian claims through its comments while declining to answer the reference. This refusal signalled the limits of judicial power in matters of faith-based historical inquiry. By contrast, in M. Siddiq, the Supreme Court awarded the entire disputed site to the Hindus, citing evidence of continuous Hindu worship and lack of exclusive Muslim possession, while also directing the allotment of 5 acres of alternate land to Muslims for a mosque. Critics argue that this outcome tilted towards majoritarian appeasement. Fourthly, the Presidential Reference preserved the Court's neutrality in an ongoing, politically charged dispute. It maintained the principle that the judiciary should not answer hypothetical or politically loaded questions. The Siddiq verdict, however, was a final and binding resolution, ending decades of litigation. Yet, events before and after the judgment suggest that it was perceived as aligning with the will of the ruling class, leaving lingering debates about secularism, majoritarianism, and judicial independence.

Conclusion

The Supreme Court's response to the Presidential Reference reinforced its image as a powerful institution, independent from political and social pressures, and as an upholder of constitutional principles. It also reaffirmed its secular character. However, the verdict in M. Siddiq (D) Thr. Lrs. v. Mahant Suresh Das & Ors brought an end to the decades-old

title dispute over the contested land, but at the same time dented the image of the judiciary. Future historical assessments are likely to highlight the weaknesses of the judiciary and critically examine the principles adopted in this judgment.

References

1. *Ismail Faruqui vs Union of India*, 1994, 6 SCC, 360.
2. *Ibid.*
3. *Jahid Hossain Bhuiyan and Darryn Jensen (eds), Law and religion in The Liberal State 217-232 (Hart Publishing, Oxford, 2020).*
4. *The Sunni Central Board of Waqfs U.P vs Gopal Singh Visharad*. OOS No. 4 of 1989 (Reg. Suit No.12-61).
5. *Ibid.*
6. *Ratna Kapur, "The Ayodhya case, freedom of religion, and the making of modernist Hinduism" 32 Contemporary South Asia 10-25 (2024).*
7. *Rachel A Varghese, "Archaeology for the courtroom: the Ayodhya Case and the fashioning of a hybrid episteme" 24 Journal of Social Archaeology 109-129 (2024).*
8. *Liberhan Commission*, available at: <https://www.mha.gov.in/en/about-us/commissions-committees/liberhan-ayodhya-commission> (Last visited on March 7, 2024).
9. *Supra note 1.*
10. *Power of President to consult Supreme Court (1) If at any time it appears to the President that a question of law or fact has arisen, or is likely to arise, which is of such a nature and of such public importance that it is expedient to obtain the opinion of the Supreme Court upon it, he may refer the question to that Court for consideration and the Court may, after such hearing as it thinks fit, report to the President its opinion thereon. (2) The President may, notwithstanding anything in the proviso to article 131, refer a dispute of the kind mentioned in the said proviso to the Supreme Court for opinion and the Supreme Court shall, after such hearing as it thinks fit, report to the President its opinion thereon. The Constitution of India, art. 143.*
11. *Ram Janma Bhumi- Babri Masjid*, AIR1993 SC 642.
12. *Ibid.*
13. *Supra note 1.*
14. *Supra note 1.*
15. *Ramesh Thakur, "Ayodhya and the Politics of India's Secularism: A Double-Standards Discourse" 33 Asian Survey 645-664 (1993).*
16. *The constitutional bench was comprised by Justice M.N. Venkatachaliah, A.M. Ahmadi, J.S. Verma, G.N. Ray, S.P. Bharucha (The opinion was unanimous).*
17. *M. Siddiq (D) Thr Lrs v. Mahant Suresh Das & Ors*, AIR (2020) 1 SCC 1: 2019 SCC Online SC 1440.